

Dynamic Programming Based Content Placement Strategy for 5G and Beyond Cellular Networks

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Abstract—Optimal caching strategies of popular contents in heterogeneous cellular networks are studied. The increasing demand for data traffic by users of the wireless network can be handled by rapaciously caching most frequently accessed contents by users. Hence, we propose an efficient popular content placement strategy, the first step in the content caching process, typically for popular video files. To do so, we introduce a novel approach for caching popular contents. This caching strategy follows a dynamic programming approach to tackle the optimization complexity of selecting most popular files among a wide range of files, under certain constraints. The proposed strategy gives the combination of popular files to be cached that maximizes the optimal cache hit probability with a pseudo-polynomial time complexity. To that end, we used the well-known resourcing algorithm, called the 0/1-Knapsack problem, assuming that files are cached without partitioning.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the heterogeneous cellular network (HCN), a small percentage of the services acquire higher popularity, at some time, and produces the largest portion of the traffic in the network. These traffic contents are vogue files which receive frequent requests from many users. Local caching of these contents, both at the radio access edge and the user equipments (UE), is very important to improve the quality of experience (QoE) in mobile networks. Content caching brings files closer to UE; thus it reduces the redundant requests of files to the backhaul network. Once the files are stored at the network edge closer to the user, i.e, the mobile helper (MH), the requests can be served by these MH. As a result, the backhaul congestion may be significantly reduced. In addition, the network response time may drastically reduce, even zero when the requested file is already cached at the UE itself. Fortunately, the advance in memory technology and the caching capability of current end-user devices renders the proposed caching strategy to be practical. The performance attained by the caching of popular contents is further enhanced by the deployment of advanced techniques such as device-to-device (D2D) communication, clustering, cooperation and coordination, transmission media control, and coded information transmission.

A. Background and Related Work

Presently, few contents are very popular and generate large percentage of the mobile traffic. Hence, in

mobile network architectures, these popular contents are locally cached in the order of their popularity. They are cached at different parts of dedicated network edges such as, macrocell base stations (BS), microcell base stations (SBS), or cache enabled UE [1]. For the past decade, the research has focused on the strategies and policies of caching popular contents to increase the cache hit and content delivery probability, the number of served requests, and decrease the response delay.

In [2], the authors analyse the gains of popular video content caching strategy in D2D communications. They evaluate the downlink traffic load reduction on the cellular backhaul attained by distributed caching scheme that uses family of admissible protocol, that handles the random file and helper association. The content exchange in the D2D link is further facilitated by a D2D-aware caching policy in work of [3]. In this policy, files are partitioned into two non-overlapping groups, which is far from the most popular content (MPC) policy. In [4], authors proposed a hybrid caching strategy where identical files are cached at each BSs while different SBS cache different files. This increases the time and spatial reuse. In fact, unplanned network densification affects increases the cost of caching. In [5] an appropriate network densification, with advanced D2D-discovery mechanism, is proposed to make the D2D communication more effective and less costly.

In [6], the authors developed a contention-based multimedia content delivery protocol, which avoids possible collision among concurrent transmissions by different active transmitters. An optimal caching mechanism is proposed based on caching the most popular files to each MH. This maximizes the successful content delivery probability to the user equipment and the coverage probability. In addition, in [7], the authors focused on cooperative caching strategy, and show that, by caching files at the off-peak time, it is possible to further enhance the performance through a broadcasting technique.

In the literature, we find three general caching approaches. The first one is cooperative caching where the helpers cooperate to cache required files and pass to the user [2], [7]–[10]. The second approach uses clustering of the network elements based on parameters such as the requested file or the cooperation distance [4], [9], [10]. The third approach is distributed caching

where the required files are stored at different tier of the network to increase the areal spectral efficiency [6], [8], [9].

The aforementioned caching strategies mainly deal with the physical parameters of the network. Beyond that, in [8], the authors proposed a systematic strategy of caching contents based on the predicted location of the UE. Indeed, as the network densification increases, this caching scheme becomes very complex and demands a robust handover decision algorithm. Hence, the predicted-location based caching can benefit the synergy of using effective handover techniques, such as the one proposed in [11]. In addition, the work in [12] presented a caching strategy based on the prediction of file popularity and future requests. This study considers the ephemerality of contents popularity while most other works stick to the static Zipf property. There are still emerging opportunistic techniques that improve content caching, based on an information theory perspective. For example, in [8], [13], [14], the authors proposed the use of mature information coding schemes in content caching strategies that can improve network performance and meet the traffic demand.

In most caching strategies, content placement is controlled by a central controller that decides which content has to be cached to which MH or UE. This is more functional in the clustered and coordinated caching techniques. In some other cases, caching is done independently: the association of a file with a UE or MH is maybe done randomly.

In the popular content caching process, we have three steps: content placement, content transmission, and content delivery. In this work, we focus only on the first step and propose an intuitive approach to improve content placement performance.

B. Motivation and Contribution

The content caching strategies developed so far focus on improving the physical parameters of the network and basically are probabilistic approaches. Most of the researches stick to constant parameters such as equal sized file fragments, static popularity distribution, and non-overlapping association. These assumptions are far from the real-time network traffic behaviour. In fact, the real time traffic dynamically changes and has extremely varying parameters. Hence, characterizing real-time mobile network is complex. Because of this, we do not have optimal content caching policy. Both the physical and content related parameters hinder the solution of optimal caching.

Here, we envision that the cellular traffic content has to be considered as a resource, when referring to the request redundancy measure. Frequently requested files are important resources. Hence, it has to be properly allocated, similarly to the radio resource allocation done in [15] and [16]. Considering as a file popularity as a resource, we introduce a new resource allocation technique to the content caching policy. To that end, we use a dynamic programming method

that can tackle the complexity of obtaining the optimal caching solution, subject to a physical parameter constraint. The approach is enumerating of files and optimizing files popularity gain, without dealing with the physical parameters of the medium. As a result, the proposed algorithm showed a high performance of caching strategy over the baseline strategies.

The contents are placed to the caching device of the network in such a way that we can maximize the gain, in our case the cumulative popularity, subject to a given constraint of the cache memory size. By using the Knapsack algorithm, we optimize the gain of the cache hit probability.

The rest part of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the system model, Section III formulates the content placement optimization problem and gives the proposed solution, and Section IV, evaluates the performance of proposed caching strategy. Lastly, Section V, contains the conclusions.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider the downlink direction of a cache enabled, three tier heterogeneous cellular network. As shown in Fig. 1, the network composes of BS, SBS, and UEs which are assumed to follow a general point process (PPP). The BS and SBS are the first and

Fig. 1: *Representative mobile network. The BS caches files, mainly during the off-peak time, to non-overlapping SBS.*

second network tiers, respectively. The BS contains set of popular video files in its finite-sized library, $M = \{\{\rho_1, l_1\}, \{\rho_2, l_2\}, \dots, \{\rho_{|M|}, l_{|M|}\}\}$ where ρ_i and l_i [MB] are the popularity and length of i^{th} file, respectively. The size of these files is not necessarily equal. Let C denote the set of the selected popular files cached in the buffer of the SBS, C , of size L , such that $C \subseteq M$. The buffer size of different SBS varies but each SBS is assumed to be capable of caching all requested files from the UEs. In this scheme, we use the terms SBS and the MH interchangeably. The UEs request files independently from the cache enabled MHs, where files are cached based on their popularity. The profile of requested files is collected by the MH from UEs. The frequency of request to a file accounts for the file's popularity, such that $\sum_{i=1}^{|C|} \rho_i \leq 1$ [17].

The popularity measure of the files is not necessarily static but may dynamically change in time.

In this work, we consider a hierarchical placement of traffic content in the cache-enabled devices; in the 5G and beyond mobile networks. A simple representation of the popular file placement is shown in Fig. 2, where the content is cached from the BS to the SBS. The files are sent to targeted SBS by selecting the best combination of candidate files, from a large set of combinatorial search space. Since the placement of the popular contents takes place during the off-peak time period, we assume that the backhaul link does not bring a performance limitation.

Fig. 2: Content placement scheme. The BS selects the best popular files that give maximum popularity at the target caching SBS.

Symbol	Definition
ρ_i	Popularity of i^{th} file
l_i	Length of i^{th} file
γ	Zipf parameter
L	Buffer size of the MH
M	Set of popular files at BS
C	Set of cached files at the helper $C \subseteq M$
$ M , C $	Number of files in M and C , respectively

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION

In this section, we present an enumerative approach for selecting the best combination of files, to be cached at the SBS, that maximizes the commutative cached files popularity. We assume that each file in M will be cached without being partitioned into sub parts, i.e., files are considered as indivisible objects, that either cached as a whole or not cached at all. Hence, the independent popularity and length for each file, we make an exhaustive search for all combinations of files that can fit the cache size, referred to as the constraint. This leads to the brute-force method which gives an optimal selection of contents from a wide range of combinatorial search space, $S = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_{|M|}\}$, where S_i is a subspace that contains exactly i files. Hence, the total search space will have $2^{|M|} - 1$ subspaces. The brute-force method gives an optimal selection but at a cost of high complexity $O(2^{|M|})$, which becomes prohibitive as $|M|$ increases. To overcome this, we use a dynamic programming (DP) approach by which

the problem is partitioned to smaller sub-problems and solved sequentially. The solution of the sub-problems is memoized for a repeated use in solving the next sub-problems. The optimal solution is found by combining these optimal sub-solutions. This process has computational complexity of $O(|M|L)$ and saves time at the cost of space. To this end, we employ an algorithm used for the well known 0/1-Knapsack problem, subject to a single constraint. This algorithm gives an optimal solution with a pseudo-polynomial time, mainly as the buffer size L gets larger [18]. In this algorithm, the file selection problem is solved by using a memoization table. Its pseudo-code is shown in Table 1, where the optimal sum of popularities of cached files is the last entry of the table. Finally, selected files can be tracked back from the memoization space.

Algorithm 1 Knapsack memoization problem

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procedure BOTTOM-UP COMPUTATION
Input:  $M = \{\{\rho_1, l_1\}, \{\rho_2, l_2\}, \dots, \{\rho_{|M|}, l_{|M|}\}\}$ 
        SBS cache size  $L$ 
for  $0 \leq j \leq L$  do
     $V[0,j]=0$ ;
end for
for  $1 \leq i \leq |M|$  do
    for  $0 \leq j \leq L$  do
        if  $j \geq l_i$  then
             $V[i, j] = \max(V[i-1, j], \rho[i] + V[i-1, j-l_i])$ 
        else
             $V[i, j] = V[i-1, j]$ 
        end if
    end for
end for
    optimal value =  $V[|M|, L]$ 

**Identify the files**
 $i=|M|+1, j=L+1$ ;
Input: temp =  $V[i,j]$ 
While  $V[i,j]>0$ 
    if  $temp \neq V[i-1, j]$  then
        select  $i^{th}$  file
         $j = j - l_i$ 
         $i = i - 1$ 
        temp =  $V[i,j]$ 
    else
         $i = i - 1$ , (do not select file)
    end if
end while

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A. Performance Metrics

The content placement strategy is basically aims at maximizing the file popularity gain at the SBS, thus, we evaluate the performance of the network by using the cache hit probability.

Cache hit probability: This is the probability that a requested file by a UE is found stored at the MH. It has been used as a measure of performance measure in

number of relevant studies (e.g. in [10], [6], [17], and [19]). The cache hit probability (Ψ) is defined as:

$$\Psi[\rho, l] = \sum_{c \in C} \rho_c \quad (1)$$

where ρ_c is the popularity of cached file c in C .

Our target is to cache as many popular files as possible to maximize the sum of file popularity at the MH. In other words, for all files whose IDs are in C , we want to obtain the maximum cache hit probability,

$$\Psi^*[\rho, l] = \max_C \sum_{c \in C} \rho_c \quad (2)$$

subject to the following one dimensional constraint:

$$\sum_{c \in C} l_c \leq L \quad (3)$$

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we evaluated the performance of the network under our strategy using simulations. We also compare the obtained performance of our strategy to that of two baseline strategies. The first baseline strategy is a greedy algorithm that caches a portion of the most popular files after it arranges the files in the descending order of their popularity. The second strategy is a random algorithm that randomly chooses the files from the search space to be cached in the SBS.

In all cases, unless otherwise stated, for the simulation we used 100 video files, of varying lengths. The files used are standard frame rate videos: a 10 minutes length SDR 720p, a 2 minutes length SDR 720p, a 2 minutes HDR 2160p(4K), and a 10 minutes HDR 2160p(4K), as recommended by Google. They have an approximate file size of 3 GB, 600 MB, 6 GB, and 30 GB, respectively. The cache size of the SBS is considered to range from 10 GB to 100 GB, which has to be less than the sum of all file sizes. We chose the Zipf parameter $\gamma = 1$, which means that the popularity is highly concentrated on a fewer number of files, and since $\gamma \geq 1$, the network will have a higher successful transmission probability [4], [8]. Next, we present the obtained results for the following three simulation results.

In the first scenario, we choose two sets of HDR 2160(4K) files with equal file sizes of 30 GB and 6 GB, independently. In both cases, the files follow a Zipf distribution. In each set, files are considered as equal sized fragments, as in [7], [9], [20]. The result in Fig. 3 shows that the performance of the greedy algorithm is similar to that of the proposed strategy. In both results, the cache hit probability decreases as the file size increases, since are able to cache smaller number of popular files. As expected, in all strategies, performance increases with the cache size. Observe from the figure that in the random strategy, the cache hit probability increases almost linearly with the cache size; this is because the random strategy performs no optimization and only tries to fit the sum of sizes of the cached files to the cache size. The proposed and greedy strategies deal with the popularity and size trade-off. Even though we increase

Fig. 3: *Scenario 1: In case 1 (upper plot), all files have a 6 GB size, and in case 2 (lower plot), all files have a 30 GB size. All files follow the Zipf popularity distribution*

the cache size, we may not fill all the space. This explains why only increasing the cache size does not always improve the cache hit probability. We can clearly see this by comparing the cases of using the 6 GB and the 30 GB files. In the first case, the files are smaller and, therefore, more files can be compacted into the cache space. As a result, in the first case, the cache hit probability is higher and behaves more strictly monotonic than the second case, where we observe a step function. This is the idea of bin packing dynamic programming. Clearly, the horizontal step size, seen in the plot, is equivalent to the file size.

In the second scenario, we use the same set of files as in the first scenario but the files have equal popularity. The results in Fig. 4 show us that the random selection of files works equally well with other two strategies, for both file sizes. This is as expected, since all files have the same popularity and size, and the selection process is the same for all algorithms. Note, however, that this is a worst-case assumption because, in real mobile networks, contents do not have the same length nor the same popularity.

The third scenario uses four groups of mixed file sizes: 600 MB, 3GB, 6 GB, and 30 GB (25% of files in the BS). We used two file popularity distributions: the Zipf and the general. In the general popularity distribution, we assumed that approximately 30% of files in the set are most popular [12], which are assumed to generate 90% of total popularity. In fact, this popularity distribution is more concentrated than the Zipf distribution

Fig. 4: Scenario 2: All files have same size (6 GB upper plot and 30GB lower plot) and equal popularity $\rho = 0.01$

with $\gamma = 1$. We further assume that both the file popularities and file sizes are independently and identically distributed (iid). To guarantee this, we reshuffled the association ten thousand times and took the mean of cache hit probability of ten iterations. This avoids the biased assignment of higher popularity to bigger files, which affects the baseline algorithms. This scenario can better represent the real-time traffic contents in the network. In this real-time scenario, content caching becomes a constrained problem and, hence, the dynamic programming approach is preferred over the greedy one.

The results in Fig. 5 clearly show that the proposed strategy outperforms, by far, the baseline strategy, for both file popularity distributions. This is because the file search to in the BS is not blocked by file sizes, under the cache size constraint. The strategy can simply check all combinations and take the maximum possible file popularity.

The proposed strategy performs better in the general popularity distribution because, in this setup, the file popularity concentrates on a smaller number of files, i.e., the file popularity is highly skewed. Hence, the popularity sum function vanishes faster in the general distribution than in the Zipf distribution. After caching these files, as far as the cache size allows, the remaining cache space is filled with many small sized files. It is also clear that, with larger cache size, we have more freedom to cache files; which means higher cache hit probability.

In this setup, the greedy algorithm has better per-

Fig. 5: Scenario 3: Varying file size and different file popularity types. Every group of 25% files has size of 600 MB, 3 GB, 6 GB, and 30 GB. Files follow a Zipf ($\gamma = 1$) and general popularity distribution

formance with the Zipf distribution at lower cache size. This is because, in the Zipf case, the popularity has the order of a formed distribution, and the selection is only taking the front groups of most popular files. With larger cache size, we have to include more files with varied file popularity. Thus, the selection becomes less effective with the greedy strategy. We also see that as the skewness of the file popularity increases, the intersection point of the two plots moves to the left. This is because, the popularity sum vanishes faster.

Also compared with scenario 1, we notice that the proposed strategy increases network performance as the file diversity is increased. The small steps in the greedy strategy function indicate the size of selected file sizes, after some free spaces in the cache. This is not seen in the proposed strategy solution, because it can effectively do the exhaustive search, which does not leave cache space gaps till the next popular file fits. Instead, it further caches other files that maybe less popular but matching size but . This further selection increases the cache hit popularity. Furthermore, the proposed solution reduces the cache memory wastage at the MHs.

In summary, the obtained results show that the cache hit probability can be highly improved by the proposed placement strategy. In addition, the proposed strategy can handle extremely diversified file sizes.

The content placement is more likely done during the off-peak time, according to the request history. In some cases, however, the content will be cached

while it is instantaneously requested by UEs. An appropriate prioritization strategy for the two options should be used here, which can increase the cache hit probability, while reducing backhaul congestion and response time.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have considered the downlink direction of the heterogeneous cellular mobile network. We have given new insights on how to deal with non-uniform parameters of the mobile data traffic such as library length, file size, and the diverse file popularity. Developing an optimal caching strategy subject to these parameters is complex. We used a dynamic programming approach to tackle this constrained optimization problem. To that end, we have used the 0/1-Knapsack problem formulation to maximize the cache hit probability under a cache size constraint. The proposed strategy outperforms the baseline algorithms. Also, the memory wastage at the MHs is reduced when using this strategy. As far the cache size allows, we can cache many popular files to the SBS by selecting from all possible file combinations. The proposed strategy can effectively handle any type of file popularity and increases content diversity. Finally, this strategy can be deployed at any network hierarchy.

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